

**Interplay between cAMP and Calcium signaling pathways in
regulating *Candida albicans* virulent responses**

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cAMP Pathway in *C. albicans*

This pathway responds to various environmental signals including glucose, CO₂, serum, and methionine (Figure 1.7.B.1). In this pathway, membrane receptors (Figure 1.7.B.2) sense these signals externally and result in cAMP-dependent (Figure 1.7.B.3) activation of Protein Kinase A, which consists of a catalytic subunit (*TPK1* and *TPK2*) (Figure 1.7.B.4) and a regulatory subunit (*BCY1*) (Figure 1.7.B.4). When cAMP binds to the regulatory domain, the signal is transferred downstream to the transcription factor *Efg1*, which then alters the transcriptional profile to promote hypha development (Figure 1.7.B.5). The elements of this pathway play an important role in regulating filamentation and cell wall biogenesis. Addition of exogenous cAMP has, for example, been shown to stimulate the yeast-hypha transition (Sabie and Gadd, 1992; Niimi, 1996). The *cyr1* mutant shows defects in the formation of hyphae and in the uptake of *C. albicans* by macrophages (Leberer et al., 2001; Rocha et al., 2001; Wachtler et al., 2011). The *tpk1* and *tpk2* mutants showed redundant roles in morphogenesis and also had a phenotype that affected interactions with epithelial cells (Park et al., 2005; Giacometti et al., 2009; Wachtler et al., 2011). The *efg1* mutant showed impaired growth on different media (Bockmuhl and Ernst, 2001). Therefore, cAMP pathways play a critical role in filamentation, growth, and cell wall biogenesis (Leberer et al., 2001).

Figure 1. 7 cAMP pathway in *C. albicans*.

Calcium Signaling Pathway in *C. albicans*

This pathway responds to changes in calcium ions present in the *C. albicans* environment. Three membrane receptors, a high-affinity calcium receptor (*Fig1*) (Figure 1.8.A.1) and two low-affinity receptors (*Cch1/Mid1*) (Figure 1.8.A.2), sense changes in calcium levels. Intracellularly, Ca²⁺ is also present in the endoplasmic reticulum and mitochondria. Extracellular Ca²⁺ ions are transported via the membrane receptors into the cytoplasm where they bind to calcium-binding protein calmodulin (Figure 1.8.A.3); this binding leads to activation of the calcium-

dependent phosphatase calcineurin, which has a catalytic domain (*Cna1*) (Figure 1.8.A.4) and a regulatory domain (*Cnb1*) (Figure 1.8.A.4). When calcineurin becomes activated, it dephosphorylates the *Crz1* transcription factor (Figure 1.8.A.5), which becomes activated and translocates to the nucleus (Rispaill et al., 2009), thereby inducing calcium-ion-dependent gene expression (Karababa et al., 2006). *Cna1* and *Cnb1* mutants showed altered virulence and restricted hypha formation (Fox and Heitman, 2002; Sanglard et al., 2003; Blankenship and Heitman, 2005; Bader et al., 2006). The *Crz1* mutant showed no obvious changes in morphogenesis and virulence (Onyewu et al., 2004). However, elements of this pathway regulate calcium intake by *C. albicans*, and this pathway is important for the transition to filamentation (Rispaill et al., 2009). This pathway has also been shown to be important for cellular orientation responses of *C. albicans* hyphae in relation to topographical and electrical field stimulation (Brand et al., 2007; Brand et al., 2008; Gonia et al., 2013). The above MAPK pathways, calcium signaling pathway, and cAMP pathway of *C. albicans* are therefore critical for the regulation of an important network of genes involved in regulating virulence properties, morphogenesis, and responses to stress imposed by the immune system as well as antifungal drug exposure (Rispaill et al., 2009; Gow et al., 2011).

Figure 1. 8 Calcium signalling pathway in *C. albicans*.

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